

Interference (Nonlocality) and NonInterference (New Physical Resonance) in Quantum Mechanics

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Interference between $\exp(ipx)$ momentum eigenstates in $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ or bound eigenstates in $W(x,t)=\text{Sum } a_n(E_n)\exp(-iE_nt) W_n(x)$ are well known in quantum mechanics. The resulting interference (seen in $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$) seems to be the effect of an OR probability condition i.e. adding complex probabilities with both the real and imaginary terms being periodic and containing both positive and negative values. (Here the wavefunction is treated as a kind of probability (i.e. a conditional probability.) In this note, we wish to argue that interference does not always occur. In particular, a free particle has a wavefunction of $\exp(-iE(p)t) \exp(ipx)$ where $E=pp/2m$, but only $\exp(ipx)$ terms interfere in $W(x)=\text{Sum } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(-iE(p)t)$ terms do not interfere, rather a new time cycling resonance is created described by an overall $\exp(-iEt)$ where E represents overall energy (kinetic and potential). In other words it seems that a new kind of energy is created namely potential energy which must be considered together with kinetic energy.

A particle in a bound state, treated as a free particle for statistical purposes, maintains a kind of identity and energy flow independent of the potential. Its energy identity, however, described by $\exp(-iE(p)t)$ where $E(p)=pp/2m$ is transformed as it now interacts with $\exp(ikx)$ terms of $V(x)$ to contribute to an overall new cycling resonance of $\exp(-iEt)$. Thus, $\exp(iE(p)t)$ terms do not interfere.

For a linear combination of bound states (e.g. in a kind of heat reservoir) $W(x,t)=\text{Sum over } n \text{ } a_n(E_n)\exp(-iE_nt) W_n(x)$ and a new cycling resonance is not created, rather the reservoir kicks one n state to another and $\exp(-iE_nt)$ terms interfere. Interference gives rise to the humps or troughs found in the original $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iE_nt)$, but no longer yields a modulus of 1 at each x or t point. Thus interference shows the nonlocality in the problem. $\exp(ipx)$ on the other hand contains both locality and nonlocality. There is a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are both nonlocal, but the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ is 1 which is a local property. Quantum mechanics allows both for interference which yields nonlocality and noninterference, e.g. $\exp(-iE_nt)$ which contains both locality and nonlocality. We investigate this idea in this note.

Locality and Nonlocality in Quantum Mechanics

Classical mechanics is well-known for its locality i.e. $x(t)$, $v(t)$ etc. Alternatively, quantum mechanics is known for nonlocality i.e. the wavefunction, frequency in time, uncertainty principle etc. Furthermore, quantum mechanics is linked to classical mechanics because for a bound state:

$$[-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}]/W + V(x) = E_n = KE_{\text{classical}}(x) + V(x) \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is a local equation showing that the quantum average of $pp/2m$ yields the classical kinetic energy at x . The free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ associated with $pp/2m$ exhibits both local and nonlocal properties. It has nonlocal features because it contains a wavelength proportional

to $1/p$ and $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are nonlocal, but its modulus is 1, ensuring that probability at each local x is 1. Furthermore, an average of $pp/2m$ yields a classical local kinetic energy value. This is not to say that quantum nonlocality is not part of the scenario because even though:

$KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = [-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}] / W$ is local, the expectation value of the kinetic energy operator $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ is not:

$$\langle W | -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} | W \rangle = \int dx \ W W [-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}] / W = \int dx \ [\text{spatial density}] \ KE_{\text{classical}}(x) \quad ((2))$$

Spatial density (x) is nonlocal and contains humps and troughs. It is completely quantum mechanical, while $KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$ is local.

A point we wish to make is that even though one begins with $\exp(ipx)$ which has a modulus of 1 (locality), a linear combination or interference of $\exp(ipx)$ terms in $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ leads to complete nonlocality. The wavefunction is now normalized as

$\int dx \ W^*(x)W(x) = 1$ which is a completely nonlocal statement in contrast to $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ which is a local statement.

Thus, there are completely nonlocal scenarios due to interference in quantum mechanics like the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$, but also probabilities which are both local and nonlocal like $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a physical resonance and so must retain a link with local space or time points in order that the idea of a probability at a point x or energy at a point x , both local concepts, make sense. Thus, quantum mechanical objects are constrained to have local features in some cases i.e.

$$\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad ((2)) \quad \text{average energy conservation} \quad [-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}] / W + V = E$$

Time in a Bound Quantum State

We argue that a bound quantum state shows both the creation of a completely nonlocal feature due to interference as well as local/nonlocal feature based on a new resonance. We have argued that $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ for a free particle represents a resonance both in space and time. In a bound state problem, different $\exp(ipx)$ interfere to create a completely nonlocal spatial density, but $\exp(-iE(p)t)$ terms where $E(p) = pp/2m$ do not. Instead a new physical resonance, associated with the cycling involved when an $\exp(ipx)$ interacts with $\exp(ikx)$ terms from $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$, is created which represents the full energy interaction. In other words, energy is not just $pp/2m$ there is also potential energy, but free particle energy flow remains p (so there is interference). One may note that $\exp(-iE_n t)$ describes a new physical resonance and that it is both local and nonlocal. The local feature is the modulus of 1 at each t point. Classically, one may associate a velocity (rms) with $KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$ which in turn may be associated with a family of classical (x,t) values. $\exp(-iEnt)$, however, seems to represent a

different time, i.e. a cycling time which holds at each t and also at each x showing that one has a non-evolving equilibrium situation.

It is interesting to see $\exp(-iEt)$ i.e. new energy with a physical cycling resonance created from stochastic hits between $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$ each which represent conditional probabilities associated with impulse hits, we argue. If one writes $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series in the time-independent Schrodinger equation, one may see this stochastic resonance more clearly:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \quad ((3))$$

For $\exp(ipx/2m t)$ it is difficult to see any physical resonance as one does not usually know the internal details of a quantum particle, say an electron, although the results of the Stern-Gerlach experiment for electron spin seem to suggest some kind of internal motion.

Example of the Time Dependent Schrodinger Equation

We have argued that in quantum mechanics one has local/nonlocal type conditional probabilities of the form $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. These carry the nonlocal feature of a wavelength or frequency, but are local in the sense that their modulus is 1 at each x or t . The locality is broken if $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$ terms interfere. In such a case a new physical resonance is not created as in the $\exp(-iEt)$ situation of a bound state where $\exp(-iEt)W_n(x)$ is already a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation.

Following (1), we consider a second time dependent case which allows for $\exp(-iEt)$ probabilities to interfere. This leads to complete nonlocality and a time-dependent spatial density because a new physical resonance is not created. In such a case, however, one sees time resolution (peaks and troughs) just as in the spatial case of $W_n(x)$ which is nonlocal, but has peaks and troughs. We consider the situation of:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n a(n) \exp(-iEnt) W_n(x) \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = \text{spatial density } (x,t)$$

Each term $\exp(-iEnt)$ represents a physical kind of cycling, but the linear combination does not lead to a new physical resonance. ((4)) seems to describe an interaction with a reservoir which kicks an n_1 system into state n_2 , but does not create a new kind of energy, say potential energy, as in the $\exp(ipx)$ states being kicked from one p to another, but with the creation of potential energy in addition. $\exp(-iEnt)$ terms interfere creating a nonlocal probability in time situation i.e. there is no overall $\exp(-iEave t)$ which has a modulus of 1 at each time t .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the idea of complex, periodic probabilities in quantum mechanics such as $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. These have a modulus of 1 at each x or t which implies locality i.e. a conservation of probability at each point or time point even though there is an underlying nonlocal structure due to the wavelength (proportional to $1/p$) or the frequency (proportional to $1/E$). In a bound state, which is a statistical scenario, one has free particle states $\exp(ipx)$ which

interact through impulse hits with $\exp(ikx)$ from $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. In fact, both the particle and the potential are on the same footing in the sense that they both represent impulse hits, but $V(x)$ contains V_k terms which serve to create a new kind of energy namely the potential energy. Thus even though a free particle represented by $\exp(ipx)$ still has an energy flow (momentum) of p , its energy is no longer $pp/2m$. Specifically:

$$pp/2m a(p) + \sum_k V(k)a(p-k) = E_n a(p).$$

Thus there seems to be a new physical cycling which occurs through the creation of the new potential energy and $\exp(-i E(p)t)$ no longer describes the physical energy cycling as it does for a free particle. (Here $E(p) = pp/2m$.) As a result, there is no interference between different $\exp(-iE(p)t)$ factors of the free particle. They do not come into the picture at all. Rather there is a new overall $\exp(-iE_n t)$ which has both local and nonlocal features. The local feature i.e. the modulus of 1 which holds at each time point shows that probability associated with cycling is constant at each time point i.e. there is a new physical resonance created.

Alternatively one may see $\exp(-iE_n t)$ terms interfering i.e. becoming completely nonlocal in the case that a new resonance is not created. In particular one may consider the reservoir type situation of $W(x,t) = \sum_n a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$. Here $\exp(-iE_n t)$ terms interfere to create a time dependent spatial density $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$.

References

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